

Review

Jennifer Thorp, *The Gentleman Dancing-Master: Mr Isaac and the English Royal Court from Charles II to Queen Anne* (Clemson, SC: Clemson University Press, 2024). 256pp. ISBN: 978-1-63-804095-8.

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Jennifer Thorp is one of the most foremost scholars working on the dancing masters of Restoration and early eighteenth-century England, and the dances they devised and taught. Her articles on the subject have included the valuable surveys ‘“Borrowed Grandeur and Affecting Grace”: Perceptions of the Dancing Master in Early Eighteenth-Century England’ (*Music in Art* 36 (Spring-Fall 2011), 9–27) and ‘Dance in Opera, 1673–1685’ (*Dance Research* 33 (Winter 2015), 93–123), as well as two preliminary articles devoted to the Restoration court dancing master that is the subject of this book: ‘Mr. Isaac, Dancing Master’ (*Dance Research* 24 (Winter 2006), 117–37) and ‘“So Great a Master as Mr Isaac”: An Exemplary Dancing-Master of Late Stuart London’ (*Early Music* 35 (2007), 435–46).

The Gentleman Dancing-Master consists of three sections. Part 1 is made up of five chapters, providing a detailed account of the ancestry, life and work of her subject, the dancing master known at the time just as ‘Mr. Isaac’. She withdraws a suggestion made in her 2007 *Early Music* article that Isaac the dancing master was related to the three musicians from a Windsor family with the surname Isaack: the brothers William (1652–1703), Peter (c.1655–94) and Bartholomew (1661–1709). Instead, she provides an impressive amount of documentation to reveal that the mysterious ‘Mr. Isaac’ was actually Francis Thorpe (c.1650–1720/1), a member of an extended family of musicians and dancing masters that included his father, grandfather and great-grandfather, who were all called Isaac Thorpe – hence Francis’s use of ‘Mr. Isaac’ as a professional name. In addition, the dancing masters Jerome Gohory and Anthony L’Abbé were apparently relatives by marriage, and Charles Burney claimed that the violinist and composer Matthew Dubourg was his illegitimate son.

Jennifer Thorp goes on to reconstruct her namesake’s career. She suggests that Francis Thorpe trained in France with his father or Jerome Gohory, and shows that after his return to England he danced in several court entertainments, including the masque *Calisto* in 1675, for which the Master of the Music Nicholas Staggins provided the music. In the 1680s he became a prominent dancing master in London, including Princess Anne (the future queen) among his pupils, and subsequently ran a dancing school in St Martin’s Lane. Mr. Isaac’s connection with Anne was to produce his lasting memorial: the series of dances specially devised for her birthday, 6 February, and apparently performed at the court balls held to celebrate the occasion. They are a lasting memorial because notated versions of 22 of them were published, mostly by John Walsh and his associates, using the Beauchamp-Feuillet system of dance notation; Isaac may have been the first dancing master working in London to use the system. Part 2 of the book is concerned with various aspects of these 22 dances, including the context of the first performances, their publishing history and the nature of their choreography and music.

Part 3 (taking up more than half the book) consists of a catalogue of the dances and their sources, followed by a complete facsimile edition of the publications with dance notation – a most valuable resource, bringing together and making available these fascinating pieces for the first time.

Anyone interested in the Restoration court and its culture will derive a lot of benefit from reading this book, but those studying the music of the period will find the relationship between Isaac and the wind player, bass violinist and composer James Paisible (c.1656–1721) particularly interesting. As Jennifer Thorp points out, Isaac and Paisible were near contemporaries; were both Catholics; and were both members of Princess Anne's household in the 1690s. Paisible is credited, mostly on the title-pages of the publications, with composing the music for 19 of Isaac's 22 surviving dances, ranging in date from *The Princess* of 1699 to *The Godolphin* of 1714, the last of the sequence of dances composed for Queen Anne's birthday; his tunes for the dances are included in the publications, running across the top of each page above the dance notation. Jennifer Thorp does not discuss how Paisible's dances might have been accompanied, but it is likely that, as with the odes specially composed for Queen Anne's birthday mostly by John Eccles and performed on the same day, they would have been played by the complete royal band, with Eccles leading the orchestra as Master of the Music.

It is unfortunate, therefore, that no four-part consort versions of these dances have yet come to light. As already mentioned, the publications with dance notation include the tunes as a running header at the top of each page, so that the phrases of the music are aligned with the sections of the dances. In two cases, *The Saltarella* (1708) and *The Royal Portuguez* (1709), two-part versions, tune and bass, were included on an extra engraved sheet in the editions, and are included in the facsimiles in this book. In addition, Thorp lists concordances in printed musical sources, which reveal that two-part versions survive of *The Favorite* (apparently the earliest of Isaac's dances, the music first published in 1688), *The Gloucester*, *The Northumberland* and *The Princess*. In addition, she points out that simple keyboard settings of *The Marlborough*, *The Royall* and *The Spanheim* were printed in John Walsh's *Second Book of the Ladys Banquet* (1706).

However, she does not list concordances with the manuscript musical sources; a full list of these would be a useful future project. To set that ball rolling: there are two-part versions (tantalisingly laid out in four-part score with the inner parts left blank) of *The Gloucester* and *The Princess* in GB-Lcm, MS 1172, ff. 45 and 46, the large anthology of theatre music, all in G minor, compiled by the prolific copyist Purcell scholars call London A. Furthermore, I am grateful to Andrew Woolley for pointing out that Charles Babel's large anthology of two-part pieces, formerly owned by Christopher Hogwood and now GB-Lbl, MS Mus. 1852/5, contains treble and bass versions of *The Princess*, *The Favourite*, *The Northumberland*, *The Richmond* and *The Rondeau*; Andrew's study of this source, 'Charles Babel's "Concerts a deux" (1702)', will appear in *Les copistes en musique en France aux XVIIe et XVIIIe siècles: travaux, ateliers, institutions*, ed. P. Denécheau and L. Guillo (Turnhout, forthcoming). Andrew also informs me that there is a simple tune-and-bass keyboard setting of *The Princess* in GB-Lbl, Add. MS 52363, pp. 12–14.

I hope that complete four-part versions of these fascinating pieces will come to light when the sources of Paisible's ensemble music are investigated more fully, or that someone will reconstruct them so that they can be performed in a manner that recreates the original circumstances of Queen Anne's birthday celebrations at St James's Palace. Jennifer Thorpe's descrip-

tions of the intricate dance patterns certainly whet the appetite. As with dances for earlier court masques and for the Restoration theatre, the music mostly consists of passages related to the social dances of the day, but often grouped into sequences of contrasted rhythms and tempi, akin to the suites of branles used in Restoration court balls. *The Britannia*, for instance, starts with a repeated minuet-like strain, followed by a repeated strain labelled 'Boree' and then a multi-section section labelled 'Minuet', while *The Gloucester* (one of the most popular, to judge from the number of musical sources) consists of four strains, two in bourée-like duple time and two in 6/4 jig-like rhythms. This pattern, using two contrasted dance rhythms, is found in a number of Isaac's dances, though some of them, such as *The Richmond* (in 3/2 with hornpipe-like musical gestures) and *The Rigadoon Royal* and *The Rigadoone* (both in duple time), remain in a single rhythm throughout.

As a musician rather than a dancer or dance historian (though with experience of providing music for historical dancers on and off throughout my career), I learned a lot from this book and can thoroughly recommend it to anyone with an interest in the Restoration court and its culture, and in the relationship between dance and music at the time. It is impressively well researched, is well thought out and easy to read, and is nicely produced in hardback, with the facsimiles of the 22 dances clearly reproduced. However, I have a couple of reservations – apart from the steep price, £115 (still £99.52 with Amazon's discount). The first is that the music was rather carelessly engraved on the original plates of the dance editions, with obvious wrong notes, missing accidentals and faulty rhythms. A few spot checks revealed that the texts in the musical concordances are rather more accurate, so it would have been useful had the reader been alerted to this problem, with an errata list provided.

More important, I was left wanting to know more about the relationship Isaac and Paisible might have had when creating these dances. Did the dancing master dictate to the composer exactly what dance patterns and rhythmic gestures he needed? Or was he presented with fully formed musical pieces to which he matched dance patterns? Or, most likely, was it a two-way collaborative process, one that might suggest a close relationship between them? This is perhaps indicated by the unusual and often complex nature of some of Paisible's tunes. *The Richmond*, for instance, plays about with small-scale hornpipe gestures in an almost obsessive way, presumably in an attempt to match the dance patterns. These are, of course, questions that anyone will have encountered who has been involved with a historically informed production of one of Purcell's major theatre works, though without the benefit of the original notated dances. I would love to see historically informed recreations of the Isaac-Paisible dances, but what would we give, for instance, to have notated versions of the original choreographies Josias Priest must have devised for the 17 dances in *Dido and Aeneas*, as performed at Chelsea in 1688?